

**CHALLENGES AFFECTING THE LEVEL OF ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE
OF GRADE 9 STUDENTS IN HORTICULTURAL CROP PRODUCTION:
BASIS FOR DEVELOPING AN INTERVENTION MATERIAL**

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Challenges Affecting the Level of Academic Performance of Grade 9 Students in Horticultural Crop Production: Basis for Developing an Intervention Material

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Abstract

This study examined Grade 9 Horticultural Crop Production students' academic struggles. This research was descriptive. Data was collected using a researcher-made questionnaire. 257 Grade 9 students from Hondagua, Lopez National Comprehensive, and Dao National High Schools in Lopez, Quezon served as the respondents of the study. The researcher used weighted mean, frequency distribution, percentage, T-test, One-way ANOVA, and Chi-square. The first and second quarters of the 2021-2022 academic year were difficult for respondents. Most responders got a numerical grade of 75%-79%. The Grade 9 Horticultural Crop Production students' challenges were learning environment, learning materials, motivation, and teaching-learning methodologies. The findings demonstrated a substantial difference between the students' demographic profile and their academic performance in Horticultural/Agricultural Crop Production and a relationship between their monthly family income and academic performance. Thus, school administrators and Horticultural Production teachers should consider students' demographics and socioeconomic level while designing programs, projects, learning materials, and activities. To make learning more relevant and improve academic success, they must be aware of the challenges that the students have faced. A parallel study on TLE specializations other than Horticultural Crop Production may address the new normal difficulties faced by students and instructors.

Keywords: *challenges, intervention materials, technology and livelihood education, horticultural crop production*

Introduction

Education's ultimate purpose is to empower an individual to do well in the field they have chosen in terms of career and life. It is said that education is an avenue of learning and training especially in educational institutions like schools, universities and colleges. As of the present days, the education's end results have declined due to the failure to maintain distinction on academics and excellence among learners and its clientele in the different educational institutions.

According to Steinmayr et al. (2017), academic performance is an essential predictor of success and well-being in adulthood, as well as the result of performance that demonstrate the degree to which a human being has achieved specific goals in school. Those who performed better in school are more likely to be active members of society, have a more fulfilling and happy life, engage in fewer illegal activities, and earn higher salaries than those who performed less well (Brown & Rigolon, 2019).

In some of the countries in the African region, the observable decline on the academic performance of the students in the previous year became an issue. Nyambe, (2018) elaborated that low academic performance of learners has become a national concern in Zambia. It is also be that there is an urgent need to have changes in the selection examination in secondary level so that it can contribute effectively to improving the quality of education in primary and secondary schools. Thus, the review of the performance of Grade 9 students from academic periods covering the year 2016 to 2019 was advised by Ilubala (2020) because it has been found that there is a low passing rate in one of the districts in Mulobezi, Zambia, in the Analysis of the results of the Mock Examination and National Examination.

The reports on the overall performance of the participants of the Philippines who represented in the conducted PISA in 2018 or the International Program for International Student Assessment Education Research significantly ranked behind among the countries in the ASEAN region in terms of mathematical, scientific literacy and reading. Among all of the said classifications, the Philippines was the last of all countries that participated in terms of rank (Almerino et al., 2020). With this, we can suggest that there is an evident decline with the performance of the students in the Philippines when it comes to academics

Based on the current situation of the students' academic performance of Hondagua National High School a secondary school under Lopez West District for the school year 2020-2021; 64 out of 247 students with a percentage equivalent of 26% of the population which comprises Grade 9 students got an average grade in TLE in the range of 75-79 while on the first and second quarter of the current school year, the data increased into 96 out of 202 students or 46% of the total population. The said data implies that there are reasons which affected the major increase in the data cited above.

Research Questions

The study focused on assessing the challenges affecting the level of academic performance of Grade 9 students in Horticultural Crop Production. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the TLE students in terms of:
 - 1.1. sex;
 - 1.2. age; and

- 1.3. family monthly income?
2. What is the level of academic performance of Grade 9 students in Horticultural Crop Production for the first and second quarter of school year 2021-2022?
3. Is there is a relationship which shows significant difference between the level of academic performance of Grade 9 students in Horticultural Crop Production with their:
 - 3.1. age; and
 - 3.2. sex?
4. Is there a significant relationship with the academic performance of Grade 9 students in Horticultural Crop Production and their family monthly income?
5. What are the challenges encountered by the respondents in mastering learning competencies in Horticultural Crop Production?
6. Based on the study's findings, what intervention material shall be suggested?

Literature Review

Demographic Profile and its relationship with academic performance

Demographic Profile as defined by Azees et al., (2020) is a personal characteristic that is used to categorize people. It includes age, gender, and income level. The study conducted by Abdul Latiff and Nasirudeen (2014) as cited by Aransi (2018) argued that gender, nationality of the student, extracurricular activities, and a desire to pursue higher degrees affected students' academic performance.

In addition, Lipa et al. (2017) also elaborated that "the demographic profile of the respondents (i.e. Age, gender and year level) affects some of the indicators to the academic performance of the students." However, there is a positive but minimal relationship between age and academic performance. It was also shown that there was a significant difference in the High School female students' academic performance in Economics.

Along with this, Dubuc et al. (2020) elaborated in their study that males and females vary in high school. This finding was also supported by the results of the study of Nwagboo et al. (2017) which revealed the outcome of their research that female students performed well as compared to male students with the same findings of the study conducted by Verbree et al. (2022) that women tend to score higher on conscientiousness than men.

Furthermore, Buctot et al. (2021) also emphasized that gender is essential in academic grades where women tend to be more enthusiastic in terms of academic success as compared to men. In contrast to the above-mentioned results of the connection of gender with academic performance, Tsalousis et al. (2019) emphasized that there is no relevant relationship with academic performance when it comes to the gender of the students. The researchers suggested that other factors which affect academic success must be further investigated.

Besides demographic profile, students' performance is correlated with socioeconomic factors such as their parents' education, occupation, income, and standard of living; students from middle- to upper-class backgrounds perform better than those from disadvantaged backgrounds. This was supported by Machebe et al.'s (2017) study, which identified the role of family income, particularly parental income, in influencing the academic performance of students. The study revealed that when the majority of parents are employed, there is less time for school-related activities, extracurricular engagement, and homework monitoring.

It was then supported by Eamon (2005), as cited by Arora (2017), that students with low socioeconomic status perform poorly in school and receive lower grades than other students. In addition, the researchers elaborated that the socioeconomic status of a student's family is believed to have a direct effect on academic achievement.

In addition, students from families with high economic profiles performed significantly better than those families from low and middle status according to the study conducted by Adetutu and Adebayo (2021). The research of Nauzeer and Jaunky (2019) indicates that students who are from families with a middle status performed better as compared to families with a low socioeconomic status. Arora (2017) also stated that a student's effective study habits and familial motivation contribute to his or her academic success. In addition, according to Buctot et al. (2021), the academic performance of students from low-income households who struggle to pay school fees is significantly diminished. Norazlan et al. (2020) discovered that because of the financial incapability to overcome financial problems, students are forced to convert the time for studies to work multiple jobs or part-time for longer hours which adversely affects their performance academically. Thu Thi Le et al. (2020) discovered that most freshmen students at universities in Vietnam seek a part-time job to adhere to the needs for expenses for school and daily living. Which affected their academic performance negatively. The same findings by Faaz and Khan (2017) demonstrated the existence of a strong and positive correlation between socioeconomic status and the academic achievement of students.

The aforementioned studies contradict the findings of Islam et al.'s (2020) study, which concluded that there is no correlation between family income and students' academic performance.

Learning environment, Learning Materials, Teaching-Learning Strategies, Motivation, and its effect on Academic Performance

According to Dhanapala (2021), the learning environment is essential because it aids the students achieve their full potential in the

learning process. He also explained that enhancing students' motivation will help them achieve academic success by providing learning spaces and classrooms with adequate materials for audio and visual study, along with technological facilities. It is said that indoor environmental quality directly affects students' health, abilities in learning, efficiency, and productivity (Kapoor et al., 2021). It was highly emphasized that students' performance and well-being are negatively impacted by inadequate thermal conditions.

In addition, the greatest challenge faced by students was associated with their learning environment at home according to Barrot et al. (2021). As evidenced by the findings, the learning environment posed the greatest obstacle for students, specifically distractions at home (e.g., noise) and space and facility constraints.

In connection with this, Cahapay (2021) elaborated that students struggle with environment-related distractions during the online assessment. Whether the noise comes from nature or a neighbor, it is argued that remote learning makes it difficult to concentrate due to environmental distractions. As explained, the sights, smells, and sounds of daily life at home make it especially difficult to concentrate. This is a serious issue with online proctored tests when these distractions are considered. Even if the teacher determines that these distractions are unrelated to dishonesty, they will still disrupt the students' concentration.

Furthermore, Naude et al. (2019) discovered that the outdoor environment's noise interferes with the teacher's lesson presentation and consequently distracts the Grade 1 students from their assigned tasks. When the teacher was forced to pause the lesson for several minutes to attend to the noise outside, the students' concentration suffered. This causes unnecessary cognitive load and hinders the optimal learning that should occur.

Also, modern learners need learning spaces that meet their own and collective needs as emphasized by Orlu (2013, as cited in Usman et al., 2019). To meet this challenge, an engaging and empowering environment that will cater to their physical and cultural needs must be prioritized by the administrators of the school. The group also discovered that environmental factors (appropriate coloring, lighting, and adequate space in schools) affect the learning achievement of students. In addition, Noor (2015, as cited by Ramos et al., 2018) also identified several factors that can improve academic performance, including air quality, and thermal comfort; sound quality; lighting; school and class sizes; building age, and quality.

Moreover, Since 2016, no SHS-STEM textbooks have been available or distributed in any public school in the entire archipelago, according to Francisco (2019). His research revealed that neither the completion nor printing of textbooks had occurred. This indicates that a lack of science textbooks has always been a significant issue in the Philippines. The absence of textbooks in teaching senior high school affects both learning and time allocation in public schools. According to Manjale and Abel (2017), instructional materials like textbooks are vital in the learning process for they help with the enhancement of the students' knowledge and participation in the learning process. This suggests that if a school lacks adequate and current learning resources, both teachers and students will have poor academic performance.

In addition, Dhanapala (2021), emphasized that learning cannot be achieved only by the teacher; students require resources and other similar sources or learning materials. Therefore, universities and educational institutions should be aware of the inclusion of learning materials and resources in the environment to facilitate easy access. Similar to Calanog (2019) where it is elaborated that teachers should prepare instructional materials with the application of the necessary pedagogical approaches to integrate teaching strategies that are innovative to increase student interest.

In her study, Kapur (2018) concluded that it is crucial to prioritize resources that are used to improve students' academic performance. During the planning phase, school administrators should account for books, handouts, learning materials, and facilities such as science and computer laboratories. When students are well-supplied with the necessary tools and equipment, they tend to have a better grasp of the subject matter's concepts, particularly those students who lack the financial means to purchase materials. In her study, she strongly suggested that the government should prioritize fund allocation. They should have more funds for the Department of Education for those secondary schools with TLE curricula that can provide more teaching materials and equipment for students.

Moreover, Tapiwa (2021) argued that the absence of school gardens, educational tours, demonstration plots, and well-equipped laboratories severely hindered the hands-on teaching of agriculture in secondary schools. These deficiencies impede more theoretical instruction than practical training, which hinders the development of practical skills. Magulod (2017) conducted a study on the factors that affect the performance and effectiveness of public and private elementary schools in the province of Cagayan and concluded that the student's task time and learning opportunity correlate with how the school provides and ensures sufficient time and materials for learning to provide effective instruction. In Lezotte's argument, it is also stated that instructional materials and time for learning must be considered. Delfino (2019) made a significant discovery in a study conducted at the Partido State University in Camarines Sur; the result demonstrated that respondents mentioned that limited or absent resources have a significant impact on academic performance. In addition, respondents elaborated that there were no materials at the school that could be used for homework or other academic enrichment activities.

Furthermore, According to de Loreto et al. (2019), one of the issues in public schools in Quezon Province is a lack of instructional materials. The study by Baliyan et al. (2021) revealed that poor teaching methods and ineffective use of learning materials by teachers are one of the obstacles to learning. McLead (2018) also found that when facilitating student activities, teachers lack the incorporation of active engagement. In addition, it is suggested that teachers should take students' abilities into account when designing lesson

activities.

In the current state of the COVID-19 pandemic, a complete shift from face-to-face to online agriculture education may not be feasible, necessitating the development of a hybrid mode in which students can participate in some out-of-class activities. In a study, Isa et al. (2020) emphasized that the majority of students' poor academic performance in various subject areas can be attributed to ineffective teaching methods employed by teachers. Icin et al. (2018) discovered that one of the challenges students face in learning is the teachers' instructional strategies.

Moreover, the group of researchers hypothesized that tailoring instructional strategies to the distinctive learning styles of students could be a proven way to improve the academic performance of students in Turkey. They added that adding activities and discussions in class regarding the learning material and readings could help student learning, thereby having a positive effect on academic performance.

In addition, Celon and Francisco, (2020) pointed out that one of the problems and challenges that affects the academic performance of the Meycauayan, Bulacan students is the utilization of the original daily strategies and methodologies by teachers and the way teachers solve unfamiliar teaching tasks can help in the revision of teaching activities' about the academic result. In connection with this, Kapur (2018) implied that students should be sincere with their studies, and have amiable and peaceful environment conditions. Teachers should be approachable in attitude and implement instructional strategies in teaching and learning as an important matter to achieve good academic outcomes.

Moreover, A study by Brew et al. (2021) revealed that students from low-income families are subjected to forced labor and have limited time to study because they value household work more than education. Dogan (2017), determined the boundary to which affected the academic motivation, engagement, and efficacy of students. The study's result highlighted mental engagement is predictive of academic performance, while emotional-behavioral engagement is not. Moreover, he discovered that academic motivation and self-efficacy have a meaningful and positive relationship with academic performance.

In Almkudad and Berhanu's (2020) study, various reasons affecting international students' academic success were identified, including students' level of hard work and commitment, and the challenges they faced, which had a significant impact on their academic performance. One student stated, "The student gets laziness, irregular class attendance, lack of class attendance, lack of revision after class, and lack of class participation; and when students study only when there is a quiz or test, they do not well master the courses and get poor performance".

In addition, according to Febriani et al. (2019), reading comprehension questions were difficult for semester students to answer because of their lack of knowledge of the material, their background, and their reading strategies. Girsang et al. (2019) referenced Mahmud (2014) as saying that high school students struggled to answer questions because they lacked the reading skills and drive. This finding is corroborated by a study conducted in 2021 by Islam et al., which highlighted the impact of students' interest and attentiveness on academic performance as one of the issues. The study's findings indicated that students who participate in class and attend at least 80% of the time, as well as those who study an additional hour or two on average each week, tend to perform well academically. This suggests that students should set aside time to study at home and engage more actively in class if they want to perform well academically. The results of Digal and Walag's (2019) study also corroborate the idea that a student's study habits play a significant role in achieving exceptional academic achievement. They go on to explain that a school in Cagayan de Oro lacks strong study habits.

Lastly, Alam and Aktar's (2021) investigation into the connection between academic achievement and the use of social media networks in general or of a specific network, like Facebook, revealed a negative relationship between social media networks and students' academic performance. Tan (2021) carried out a study that concentrated on the crucial elements of teaching TLE that need to be taken into account, such as curriculum enrichment and adaptation to changes, the use of modern, functional equipment, teaching techniques and methodology, and the use of efficient instructional materials. Teachers of language exchange programs must ensure the sufficiency and efficiency of the tools and educational resources they use. It was suggested that teachers teaching livelihood must ensure the important materials and equipment are relevant and contribute to effective teaching and learning. Ramos (2021) cited the result of a study conducted by Omekwe (2009) that resources such as instructional materials and human resources must be available to the schools.

Intervention Materials in Improving Students' Academic Performance

According to Asio and Jimenez (2020), teachers start remediation exercises for their students based on their academic performance. They then use interventions and strategic strategies to boost the students' retention of the material. Balinas et al. (2017) also showed that the intervention had a good effect on participants' performance; a significant difference was seen between the pre- and post-test scores. In contrast to these results, Sommerhalder (2018) showed in his study that the implementation of intervention materials had no effect on the academic performance of the students in the subject of mathematics. Moreover, Wang et al. (2017) state that one of the most difficult problems in remediation research and practice is still its efficacy. As stated by Obaga et al. (2017), preventing pupils from feeling excluded is one of a teacher's most significant duties. This can be achieved, in part, by our activities and by regularly assessing the climate in the school. In addition, educators need to be able to analyze and interpret the data collected from children who are going through a transition and understand how pupils interact with their surroundings.

In addition, according to a research by Sinco (2022) on strategic intervention materials, students who used these tools to learn concepts

they had not previously learned were able to achieve higher scores. The majority of intervention materials now include exercises that help students build higher order cognitive abilities; lively, fascinating, and understandable topic discussions; and resources that, when utilized by students, ensure comprehension as a consequence of the research done by Lazo et al. (2021).

In addition, remediation and intervention have a significant impact on pupils' academic achievement, according to Asio & Jimenez (2020). According to Suarez & Casinillo (2020), SIM should be included in the Science curriculum to help students with challenging ideas and enhance their academic performance. SIM appears to be a useful instrument for information transfer to students and helps them acquire the foundational knowledge, abilities, and comprehension in the science subjects that they have not mastered the most. This validates Bete's (2020) study's finding that SIM can enhance scientific education and raise students' academic achievement.

Furthermore, remediation and intervention have a significant impact on pupils' academic achievement, according to Asio & Jimenez (2020). According to Suarez & Casinillo (2020), SIM should be included in the Science curriculum to help students with challenging ideas and enhance their academic performance. SIM appears to be a useful instrument for information transfer to students and helps them acquire the foundational knowledge, abilities, and comprehension in the science subjects that they have not mastered the most. This validates Bete's (2020) study's finding that SIM can enhance scientific education and raise students' academic achievement.

Lastly, Alboruto (2017) underlined that enhancing process skills and idea mastery in science can be achieved through the use of tools for intervention managing excessively high class sizes. Student performance is improved by the project. Affuso and co. Al. (2022) highlighted in the study's findings that parents' constant observation and instructors' assistance had an indirect impact on students' academic achievement over time. These indicate that student performance can be improved by offering treatments targeted at enhancing parental and teacher supervision and support.

Methodology

Research Design

A descriptive-correlational research design was used in the study. The study aimed to identify the relationship between the variables of the study. In order to maintain the objectivity of the study, the researcher utilized quantitative research technique.

Respondents

The respondents of the study are the students taking up Horticultural Crop Production as specialization subject in Technology and Livelihood Education in the 9th Grade. The researcher had chosen three secondary schools from Lopez West District namely: Hondagua National High School, Lopez National Comprehensive High School and Dao National High School. The gathering of data was done through the utilization of an online survey questionnaire.

Simple random sampling was used to get the number of respondents. According to Bhardwaj (2019) in random sampling, "the members of the sample are selected randomly and purely by chance. Hence, the quality of the sample is not affected as every member has an equal chance of being selected in the sample. This type of sampling is best for population which is highly homogenous. (p.158)" With the use of slovin's formula with a 95% confidence level, the researcher was able to determine the total number of students which are the subject of study in each respective school.

The researcher was able to come up with a total of 257 respondents from the schools above mentioned. The distribution of the respondents per school were 133 who came from Hondagua NHS, 96 from Lopez National Comprehensive HS and lastly, 28 for Dao NHS.

Instruments

This study used a four-point likert scale as a research Survey instrument in the form of google form, a survey administration software on the internet. The research instrument was a self-made material by the researcher to gauge the level of academic performance and challenges faced during learning the competencies in TLE. Questionnaires used in the collection of data was in the form of a descriptive survey. It aimed to evaluate, interpret and show the data in the current situation.

Procedure

The research instrument in the form of an electronic survey questionnaire via Google Forms was produced. The necessary permits were secured from the Division, District, and School Offices before the conduct of the study. After permits have been secured, proper communication with the school head and concerned teachers of the respective schools where the study was intended to take place was done. After the necessary steps was made, the researcher started the administration of the questionnaire checklist with the respondents.

The interpretation of data came after the retrieval, tallying, tabulation, calculation, and analysis. The assistance of the statistician, consultant, and adviser's assistance were enlisted in order to come up with a great write-up of the manuscript for the final defense. The findings were summarized, and conclusions and suggestions were made. Following the oral defense, appropriate modifications will be made, considering the oral examination committee's comments. There will be hardbound copies submitted.

Ethical Considerations

Before gathering data from the respondents, the researcher ensured that the respondents are informed and aware of the things that are included in their undertaking. Including their full consent to participate in the said study, the usage of the information which they have provided but with the assurance of the confidentiality of it.

The study was conducted to help the respondents and the educational community. The Intervention material aims to help and improve the academic performance of students who had difficulties. This study does not inflict any forms of harm to the respondents.

Results and Discussion

In this section, interpretation, analysis and presentation of data are discussed in accordance with the result of the study. The study assessed the challenges faced by of Grade 9 students in Horticultural Crop Production of Lopez West District in Lopez, Quezon correlated with the learner's profile and academic performance. The result of this served as the basis for making instructional material.

The following data was collected for the age profile of the students:

Table 2. Profile of the Respondents in Terms of Age

<i>Age</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent (%)</i>
14-15 years old	160	62%
16-17 years old	96	37%
18-19 years old	1	1%
Total	257	100%

Table 2 divulges the frequency and percentage distribution among the respondents with their age. It discloses that majority of the respondents belong to the 14-15 age bracket, with the highest frequency of 160 or 62 percent. With 37 percent, 96 were in the 16-17 age bracket, while only 1 or 1 percent were in the 18-19 age bracket. This implied that most of the respondents' age were appropriate for the grade level they are currently in.

The following data was collected for the sex profile of the students:

Table 3. Profile of the Respondents in Terms of Sex

<i>Sex</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent (%)</i>
Male	158	62%
Female	99	38%
Total	257	100%

Table 3 revealed the distribution of frequency and percentage among respondents as to their sex. Most of the respondents were male, comprised of 158 or 62 percent of the total population, and the female respondents had a total population of 99 or 38 percent. This insinuated that most of the Horticultural Crop Production students of Lopez West District were male, which indicated that the percentage of male students who responded to the questionnaire is higher as compared to female.

The following data was collected for the monthly family income of the students:

Table 4. Profile of the Respondents in Terms of Monthly Family Income

<i>Monthly Family Income</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent (%)</i>
Below 10,000	174	68%
10,001-20,000	45	18%
20,001-30,000	23	9%
30,001-40,000	9	4%
40,001 and above	6	2%
Total	257	100%

Table 4 presents the data of the respondents in with their family of monthly income. It can be seen from the table that 174 out of 257 respondents or 68 percent have below 10,000 monthly incomes. Seconded by 10,001-20,000 monthly income with a frequency of 45 or 18%. Then the monthly income of 10,001-20,000 with a frequency of 45 or 18%. The respondents which belong to a family with a monthly income of 20,001-30,000 had a frequency of 23 or 9%. Lastly, followed by respondents which belong to a family with a monthly income of 30,001-40,000 comprised of 9 respondents or 4%. However, the respondents which belongs to a family with a monthly income of 40,000 and above obtained the lowest frequency of 6 or 2%.

This data implied that most of the respondents belong to a family living below the margin of poverty. As a result, parents tend to have problems sending their children to educational institutions because of the needed finances of their child from going to school and supplies. If the child is financially affected, it could have worst effects to their performance in school because of the stress of not having enough finances to support them.

The following data was collected for the level of academic performance of Grade 9 students in Horticultural Crop Production for the

first and second quarter of school year 2021-2022:

Table 5. Students' Academic Performance for the 1st Quarter

Grade	Frequency	Percent (%)
Outstanding (90-100)	45	18%
Very Satisfactory (85-89)	45	18%
Satisfactory (80-84)	51	19%
Fairly Satisfactory (75-79)	116	45%
Total	257	100%

Table 5 illustrates the students' academic performance, which is based on their first quarter grades. It depicts that the majority of the students got a grade of "fairly satisfactory" (75-79) with a frequency of 116 or 45 percent, followed by the grade of "satisfactory" (80-84) with a frequency of 51 or 19 percent, whereas the outstanding (90-100) and very satisfactory (85-89) gained the lowest frequency of 45 or 18 percent.

These data suggest that most of the students were just able to pass. Their academic performance shows that those students who are at risk of failing might fail if there is no intervention or action should be taken by the teacher to improve the students' academic performance.

Table 6. Students' Academic Performance for the 2nd Quarter

Grade	Frequency	Percent (%)
Outstanding (90-100)	52	20%
Very Satisfactory (85-89)	41	16%
Satisfactory (80-84)	49	19%
Fairly Satisfactory (75-79)	115	45%
Total	257	100%

Table 6 exemplifies the students' academic performance for the 2nd quarter. It indicates that the majority of the students have a grade of fairly satisfactory (75-79) with a frequency of 115 or 45% as same as the first quarter grade, followed by the outstanding (90-100) with a frequency of 52 or 20%, satisfactory (80-84) with a frequency of 49 or 19%, and lastly, very satisfactory (85-89) with a frequency of 41 or 16%. It is noticeable that there was almost no improvement in academic performance in the previous grade of the 1st quarter.

The following data was collected for the significant difference between the level of academic performance of Grade 9 students in Horticultural Crop Production with their age:

Table 7. Difference Between Students' Academic Performance and their Age

Components	F-value	p-value	Decision	Remarks
1 st Quarter Grade	14.205	.000	Reject H ₀	Significant
2 nd Quarter Grade	12.785	.000	Reject H ₀	Significant

Decision rule: "If p-value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05), reject H₀; otherwise failed to reject H₀."

Table 7 reveals the difference between students' academic performance and their age. As presented in the table, the 1st and 2nd quarter grades have the same significance level, less than 0.05, rejecting the null hypothesis, implying that age significantly affects the student's academic performance.

It is then concluded that the difference between students' academic performance and their age is statistically significant. The differences in the experiences of the students who were older students affected positively in their performance in academic settings. The results are closely similar to the results of the study of Abdul Latiff and Nasirudeen, (2014) as cited by Aransi, (2018) revealed a positive but weak linear relationship existed between age and academic performance.

It was also backed up by the study of Lipa et al., (2017) also which states that "the demographic profile of the respondents such as age, gender, and year level affects in some of the indicators to the academic performance of the students."

The result to this problem will help contribute to the body of knowledge. It will help teachers in crafting the learning activities that will suit the age profile of the students. It is important for the members of the academe to plan and craft learning activities that will enhance and unlock the full potential of each student which result into more ideal level of academic performance.

The following data was collected for the significant difference between the level of academic performance of Grade 9 students in Horticultural Crop Production with their age and sex profile:

Table 8. Difference Between Students' Academic Performance and their Sex

Components	t-value	p-value	Decision	Remarks
1 st Quarter Grade	10.254	.000	Reject H ₀	Significant
2 nd Quarter Grade	10.328	.000	Reject H ₀	Significant

Decision rule: "If p-value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05), reject H₀; otherwise failed to reject H₀."

Table 8 displays the difference between students' academic performance and their sex. It can be observed that the computed significant values of the variables for the 1st quarter and 2nd quarter grades are significant since the computed values are (t-10.254, p-.000) and

($t=10.328$, $p<.000$), which are less than the 0.05 level of significance.

Results suggest that differences exist in the mental functioning of boys and girls when it comes to academics. The result implies that sex is significantly related to their performance and potentially affects students' academic performance. The findings of are similar with the study conducted by Dubuk et al., (2020); Nwagboo et al., (2017); Verbree et al. (2022); and Buctot et.al., (2021). In contrast, the results of the study conducted by Bullalon III et al. (2019) it showed that gender has no relationship with academic performance on the subject areas.

The result to this problem will contribute to the body of knowledge. It will help teachers in crafting the learning activities that will consider the gender differences of the students. It is important for the teachers to make learning activities sensitive to the gender of the students. This may help with the improvement the academic performance of the students because students tend to be more engaged if the learning activities are sensible to their gender.

The following data was collected for the significant relationship with the academic performance of Grade 9 students in Horticultural Crop Production and their family monthly income:

Table 9. *Relationship Between Students' Academic Performance and their Monthly Family Income*

Components	Chi-square value	p-value	Decision	Remarks
1 st Quarter Grade	104.643	.000	Reject H_0	Significant
2 nd Quarter Grade	86.954	.000	Reject H_0	Significant

Decision rule: "If p-value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05), reject H_0 ; otherwise failed to reject H_0 ."

Table 9 expresses the relation between students' academic performance and their family's monthly income. Based on the computed values of the variables ($t=104.643$, $p<.000$) for 1st quarter grade and ($t=86.954$, $p<.000$) for 2nd quarter grade, it can be remarked that the family monthly income significantly affects the students' academic performance for the 1st and 2nd quarter. This indicates that there is a linear relationship between these variables.

Similar to Faaz and Khan's study, the result suggests that families' financial position and students' academic performance are strongly correlated (2017). The result suggests that socioeconomic status—parents' education, career, income, and way of living—affects student performance (Machebe et al., 2017). Adetutu and Adebayo (2021) found that students from typical socio-economic families outperformed those from low-income ones.

However, students without financial resources struggle to pay fees, find time to study due to part-time jobs (Thu Thi Le et al., 2020, 2017; Yusuf 2020), and gain inspiration from parents (Arora, 2017), resulting in poor academic achievement.

The result to this problem will contribute to the body of knowledge. It will help teachers align their learning activities based on the financial capability of the students. They may utilize learning activities which will not exhaust the finances of the students. Activities which use local or indigent resources so that students will not have problems with the accomplishment of the requirements in the subject.

The following data was collected for the challenges encountered by the respondents in mastering learning competencies in Horticultural Crop Production:

Table 10. *Challenges Encountered by the Respondents in Terms of Milieu or Learning Environment*

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. There is noise coming from the environment	3.22	Agree
2. There is not enough space for learning at home.	2.84	Agree
3. There is no enough lighting at home.	2.61	Agree
4. There is no proper ventilation at home.	2.67	Agree
5. No one helps/guides me in accomplishing the learning tasks.	3.00	Agree
Over-all Mean	2.87	Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.75 Strongly Disagree, 1.76-2.50 Disagree, 2.51-3.25 Agree, 3.26-4.00 Strongly Agree

It can be observed from table 10 that the challenges encountered by the respondents in terms of milieu or learning environment. Based on the dataset, respondents "agree" on all the given indicators with an overall mean of 2.87. The indicator "there is noise coming from the environment" was among the challenges encountered by the respondents, obtaining the mean of 3.22 with an interpretation of "agree," followed by the indicator "no one helps/guides me in accomplishing the learning tasks" with a mean of 3.00, which also has a verbal interpretation of "agree." On the other hand, "there is not enough lighting at home" has the lowest mean of 2.61, which is verbally interpreted as "agree."

Learning environment is said to be important because it helps students unlock the full effectiveness in the process of learning, with accurate and adequate facilities for every study condition, classrooms with enough learning spaces, and electronic facilities in learning which student motivation which lead to academic success (Dhanapala, 2021).

The above reflected challenges regarding the Mileu or Learning environment shows that factors such noise coming from the outside environment (Cahapay, 2021; Naude et al., 2019), ideal learning spaces (Kapoor et al., 2021; Orlu, 2013, as cited in Usman et al.,

2019), proper lighting and ventilation (Noor, 2015, as cited by Ramli et al., 2018), and guidance within the family were the challenges which affected the academic performance students.

The result to this problem will contribute to the body of knowledge. It will help school administrators and teachers realize the effect of the environment where the students are learning. It may be used as a reference on what facilities are needed to be improved and what strategies will they be making in order to make these improvements feasible.

Table 11 shows the challenges encountered by the respondents in terms of Learning Materials, with an overall mean value of 2.49 and a verbal interpretation of “agree.” It is remarkable to note that, “the availability of learning materials is limited” garnered the highest mean of 2.83, the only indicator with a verbal interpretation of “agree.” Conversely, all the remaining indicators are verbally interpreted as “disagree” such as, “the contents of the learning materials are not readable” (\bar{x} =2.42), “the learning materials are not aligned with the objectives” (\bar{x} =2.41), “the learning materials do not cover the necessary information about the topic” (\bar{x} =2.39), and lastly, “the learning materials do not contain engaging/feasible activities” has the lowest mean (\bar{x} =2.38).

Nevertheless, it is noticeable that there is a small difference in the average rating on the aforementioned four indicators.

Table 11. *Challenges Encountered by the Respondents in Terms of Learning Materials*

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1.The availability of learning materials is limited.	2.83	Agree
2. The learning materials are not aligned with the objectives.	2.41	Disagree
3.The learning materials do not contain engaging/feasible activities.	2.38	Disagree
4. The contents of the learning materials are not readable.	2.42	Disagree
5. The learning materials do not cover the necessary information about the topic.	2.39	Disagree
Over-all Mean	2.49	Disagree

Legend: 1.00-1.75 Strongly Disagree, 1.76-2.50 Disagree, 2.51-3.25 Agree, 3.26-4.00 Strongly Agree

Learning cannot be achieved with just the help of the teacher alone, students need resources and other similar sources or learning materials for learning (Dhanapala, 2021). The result implies that the availability of learning materials is the top-most challenge that the students have which affected their academic performance the results are the same as the study done by Francisco (2019) that the absence of books especially the books related to agriculture (Chinooneka, 2019), availability of proper tools and equipment to be used (Kapur, 2018), and inadequate space for laboratory hinders training for practical skills which employs more on theoretical teaching which limits the development of hands on skills which has an adverse effect on students' learning.

The result to this problem will contribute to the body of knowledge. It will help school administrators and teachers realize the effect of the presence of the learning resources to the students' performance academically. It may be used as a reference on which proper learning material should be provided to the students to help them reach the maximum learning potential and the meaningful acquisition of the needed competencies.

Table 12. *Challenges Encountered by the Respondents in Terms of Motivation*

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. The learning activities are not engaging.	2.49	Disagree
2. The learning activities do not activate my prior knowledge.	2.47	Disagree
3. The learning activities do not promote my higher order thinking skills.	2.47	Disagree
4. My attention gets easily diverted to other things like social media and online games.	2.90	Agree
5. I find it hard to do school works and household chores at the same time.	3.11	Agree
Over-all Mean	2.69	Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.75 Strongly Disagree, 1.76-2.50 Disagree, 2.51-3.25 Agree, 3.26-4.00 Strongly Agree

In terms of motivation, table 12 displays the challenges encountered by the respondents. As presented in the table, the indicators “I find it hard to do school works and household chores at the same time” (\bar{x} =3.11), and “my attention gets easily diverted to other things like social media and online games” (\bar{x} =2.90) gained the highest mean.

In contrast with the indicators “the learning activities are not engaging” (\bar{x} =2.49), “the learning activities do not promote my higher order thinking skills” (\bar{x} =2.47), and “the learning activities do not activate my prior knowledge” (\bar{x} =2.47), respectively. The mentioned three indicators have a verbal interpretation of “disagree.” Overall, challenges in terms of motivation is identified as “agree” with a mean of (\bar{x} = 2.69).

“Motivation is seen as the person's effort to accomplish duties, dedicating the needed effort and continuing it. It plays a significant role in an individuals' educational life and their achievement because it reflects in the choices in terms of academic works, the time and effort they put into to each task, and lastly, their perseverance in academic tasks” (Muhammad et al., 2021).

The results shows that most students had hardship in managing their personal time and academic time. Most of the students cannot focus on doing the learning tasks because of the chores to do at home, this was supported by the study of Brew et al., (2021) where students do not have ample time to study and this happens because they prioritize household work better than school.

Another challenge that affected the students' academic performance is that the students tend to spend time on social media and other

online games. With the support of the findings of the study conducted by Giunchiglia et al. (2018) which confirmed that long period of the use of social media applications had a negative effect of the performance of the students.

This was supported by the study made by Jamil et al., (2020) where they had found out that “more time spent on social media in 24 hours affects the study timings negatively thus affecting the study outcome and academic results.”

The result to this problem will contribute to the body of knowledge. It will help school administrators and teachers realize the relevance of learner’s engagement to learning. It may be used as a reference on how teachers can plan activities that will awaken the students’ interest with the topic which can result to a more positive result on the academic performance.

Table 13. Challenges Encountered by the Respondents in Terms of Matter or Teaching-Learning Strategies

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
1. I rely on the internet in doing the learning tasks.	2.50	Disagree
2. I prefer doing the activities that are more feasible to be done at home.	2.47	Disagree
3. I rely on asking my teachers for further explanation in understanding the context of the learning material.	2.91	Agree
4. I rely on asking other people for the translation of the instructions so I can understand the context of the learning materials.	2.74	Agree
5. It is challenging to cope up with the activities when it is not suitable with my capability.	3.38	Strongly Agree
Over-all Mean	2.8	Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.75 Strongly Disagree, 1.76-2.50 Disagree, 2.51-3.25 Agree, 3.26-4.00 Strongly Agree

Table 13 indicates challenges encountered by the respondents in terms of matter encountered by the students, with the highest computed mean of 3.38, which is verbally interpreted as “strongly agree.” Followed by the indicators, “I rely on asking my teachers for further explanation in understanding the context of the learning material” (\bar{x} =2.91), “I rely on asking other people for the translation of the instructions so I can understand the context of the learning materials” (\bar{x} =2.74) which are interpreted as “agree”, and lastly, the indicators which got the lowest mean are, “I rely on the internet (\bar{x} =2.50) “I prefer doing the activities that are more feasible to be done at home” (\bar{x} =or Teaching-Learning Strategies with an overall weighted mean of 2.80. It can be gleaned from the table that the indicator “It is challenging to cope up with the activities when it is not suitable with my capability” is the most challenging thing 2.47) are interpreted at “Disagree.”

According to Celon and Francisco, (2020) “teachers use instructional strategies to help students become more independent and tactical learners. These strategies are said to become effective when students chose the suitable learning strategies according to their needs, capabilities, interest, and characteristics and use them to accomplish learning tasks.”

These strategies used for instruction can energize students and help them focus and apply information to result to a better academic performance.

The results showed that in terms of the teaching-learning strategies there was indeed a challenge that the students have experienced. First on the list is the suitability of the learning tasks on the capability of the students, a study by Karunanayake et al., (2020) suggested that the teacher should provide those students who are having difficulties in learning relevant teaching materials’ and give learning tasks that are simpler to suit the students’ capability and give remediation for those who are at risk of failing.

It is then followed by the challenge in terms of understanding of the context of the learning materials which results to the dependence on follow up with the teacher and other MKO or more knowledgeable others at home. It was the same results of the study conducted by Febriani et al., (2019) the problems faced by students were absence of students’ background and understanding of the read text and the lack of the strategies in reading which resulted to the failure on answering questions which needs comprehension.

The result to this problem will contribute to the body of knowledge. It will help teachers realize the effect of the strategies that they are using. It may be used as a reference to evaluate the effectivity of the learning strategies applied and decide on which teaching strategies should be improved because it has been effective and should be changed.

Conclusion

This research aimed to identify challenges faced by Grade 9 Horticultural Crop Production students in Lopez West District. With the results given by the respondents, the researcher was able to conclude the following: The majority of Grade 9 Horticultural Crop Production students of Lopez West District is composed of students in the age bracket of 14-15 years old. The number of male students is greater than female population of grade 9 students taking up Horticultural Crop Production in Lopez West District and belongs to a family household who earns below 10,000.00 monthly.

The respondents’ academic performance in the first and second quarter in majority falls under fairly satisfactory with numerical equivalent of 77-79 percent. The demographic profile such as age and sex of the respondents significantly differs with the respondents’ academic performance. This concludes that there is a difference in the cognitive-motivational functioning of boys and girls in the academic environment.

The monthly family income significantly affects the academic performance of the respondents. This reflects that the lack of capability of the family to provide for the educational materials needed by the respondents can have adverse effects on the performance in school.

Based on the dataset, Teaching and Learning Strategies, Motivation, learning environment, and materials, respectively, are the challenges that respondents have encountered. Intervention materials can be utilized by the teacher to help improve the academic performance of the students taking up Horticultural Crop Production.

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